

CYBERLENINKA

BASE

OpenAIRE

Google Scholar

SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Sharipova Shaxnoza Savriddin qizi

SUG'URTA TERMINLARINING LEKSIKOGRAFIK TADQIQI

DRJI

Universal
Impact Factor

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

2023-2024

zenodo

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

ADVANCED SCIENCE INDEX